

Perspectives on coffee culture: Ge'ez conundrums

Ethiopia is the cradle of coffee culture, yet early evidence for it is scant. Does the Ge'ez word for coffee reveal clues? I propose an etymological link to the Zoroastrian Emperor of Persia, Khosrow I (or II), reflecting contemporaneous Aksumite 'anti-coffee' sentiments.

Ge'ez, used in Ethiopian Orthodox Tewahedo liturgy since the fourth century, is traced to the first century emergence of Aksum⁽¹⁾. Ge'ez for coffee is *Etse Kusra/Khusra* (Etse=plant)⁽²⁾. Few early manuscripts exist⁽¹⁾. The fifteenth century *Dārsanä Şəyon* probably reflects earlier traditions: coffee is described as 'a devilish evil tree'; *kusra* as traded with Moslems but strictly forbidden for Christians⁽³⁾.

Tadesse⁽²⁾ links *kusra* to Asian words, including eunuch. In Persian, *kusra* can mean 'the habit of drinking much wine'⁽⁴⁾. Semantic shifts from 'wine' to 'coffee' are noted in other languages. Alternatively, or concomitantly, the origin could be a name. Likely an enemy: *kusra* shares the Ge'ez consonants of 'abominable'⁽³⁾.

Khosrow I 'Anushirvan' was a powerful enemy in the sixth century, so was his grandson Khosrow II 'Parviz' in the seventh. Transliterations of Khosrow include 'Khusrau'⁽⁵⁾ and 'Khusra'⁽⁶⁾. Furthermore, Anushirvan likely knew of coffee. He ousted Aksum from Yemen, and actively sought out medical knowledge from other cultures⁽⁵⁾.

References:

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